

Studies in Azides. Part I. Replaceability of Azido Group in Nitrophenylazides

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A few phenylazides have been prepared and, when allowed to react with ammonia and hydrazine hydrate, are converted into the corresponding amines and hydrazines.

A nitro group not only activates a halogen atom in its *ortho* or *para* position in nitro-halogenobenzenes¹, but also confers mobility to another nitro group, when similarly situated².

The activating influence of the nitro group on the displacement of an azido group in suitably substituted benzene derivatives has not been much studied. In the present investigation, the displacement reaction of several nitrophenylazides have been studied. For this purpose 4-chloro-2,6-dinitro-, 2-chloro-4,6-dinitro-, 4-bromo-2,6-dinitro-, and 3-methyl-2,4,6-trinitro-phenylazides were prepared from 1,4-dichloro-2,6-dinitro-,³ 1,2-dichloro-4,6-dinitro-³, 1-chloro-4-bromo-2,6-dinitro-⁴, and 3-chloro-2,4,6-trinitro-1-methyl benzenes⁵ respectively by their reaction with sodium azide in aqueous acetone solution. 2-Iodo-4-nitro- and 4-iodo-2-nitro-phenylazides were prepared by adding an aqueous solution of sodium azide to a cooled diazotised solution of 2-iodo-4-nitro- and 4-iodo-2-nitro-aniline respectively.

When the nitrophenylazides are allowed to react with ammonia and hydrazine hydrate, the azido group is replaced by $-NH_2$ and $-NHNH_2$ respectively to yield the corresponding anilines and hydrazines. The yields of the anilines obtained (cf. Table II) indicate that nuclear azido group, which is generally quite firmly linked, is activated when there is one nitro group in its *ortho* or *para* position and becomes quite marked when two or more such groups are present. The remarkably poor yields in cases of 4-chloro-2,6-dinitro- and 4-bromo-2,6-dinitro-phenylhydrazines are due to their ease of cyclisation to the corresponding hydroxybenzotriazoles, which are formed in 62 and 65% yield respectively along with them⁶.

1. Pisani, *Annalen*, 1854, 92, 326; Korner, *Gazzetta*, 1874, 4, 305; Beilstein and Kurbatow, *Annalen*, 1876, 182, 99, 108, etc.
2. Mangini and Deliddo, *Gazzetta*, 1933, 63, 625; Le Fevère and Turner, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 750.
3. Ullmann and Sane, *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 3730.
4. Sane and Joshi, *this Journal*, 1933, 10, 459.
5. Ullmann and Nadaj, *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 1818.
6. Joshi and Deorha, *this Journal*, 1952, 29, 545; 1957, 34, 14.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Chloro-2,6-dinitrophenylazide.—To a solution of 1,4-dichloro-2,6-dinitrobenzene (5 g.) in acetone (25 ml) was added a solution of sodium azide (2.5 g.) in the minimum amount of water. The mixture was refluxed on a water bath for about an hour. On dilution with water, a solid separated. The residue after filtration was washed with water. On crystallisation from ethanol, it afforded 4-chloro-2,6-dinitrophenylazide (4 g.), m.p. 84-85° (decomp.).

Following the same procedure, 2-chloro-4,6-dinitro-, 4-bromo-2,6-dinitro-, and 3-methyl-2,4,6-trinitro-phenylazides were also prepared (Table I).

TABLE I

Characteristics of phenylazides.

No.	Phenylazide.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
1	4-Chloro-2,6-dinitro.	85°	Colorless	$C_6H_2O_4N_5Cl$	Cl: 14.39%	14.58%
2	2-Chloro-4,6-dinitro.	64°	„	$C_6H_2O_4N_5Cl$	Cl: 14.43	14.58
3	4-Bromo-2,6-dinitro.	91°	„	$C_6H_2O_4N_5Br$	Br: 27.61	27.78
4	3-Methyl-2,4,6-trinitro.	90°	Light brown	$C_7H_4O_6N_6$	N: 31.12	31.34
5	2-Iodo-4-nitro.	62°	Pale yellow	$C_6H_3O_2N_4I$	I: 43.55	43.79
6	4-Iodo-2-nitro.	72°	„	$C_6H_3O_2N_4I$	I: 43.61	43.70

2-Iodo-4-nitrophenylazide.—To a well-cooled solution of 2-iodo-4-nitroaniline (5 g.) in HCl (conc., 20 ml) was added a solution of sodium nitrite (3.5 g.) in water (8 ml) in three portions, the temperature being maintained below 5°. The excess of nitrous acid was removed by the addition of urea. To the filtered diazonium chloride solution was added a solution of sodium azide (3.5 g.) in water (10 ml) with efficient cooling and stirring. Pale yellow crystals of 2-iodo-4-nitrophenylazide separating after a few minutes were washed with water and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 62°.

4-Iodo-2-nitrophenylazide was prepared in the same way as above, starting from 4-iodo-2-nitroaniline (Table I).

Reaction with Ammonia.—Dry ammonia was passed into a boiling ethanolic solution of the reactive azido compound (0.01 *M*) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.03 *M*). After 1½ hour in cases 1, 2, 3, and 4 (Table I), the products separated during the reaction.

The products 5 and 6 remained in ethanol. On dilution with water, the solid separating was extracted with HCl (dil.). The acid extract on basification furnished the required products. These anilines have been characterised by preparing the acetyl and benzoyl derivatives (Table II).

TABLE II

*Phenyl-azide used.	Aniline formed.	Yield.	M.P.	Colour.	Derivative.	M.P.	Found.	Reqd.
1	4-Chloro-2,6-dinitro-7	65%	140°	Yellow	Acetyl	215°	Cl : 13.44%	13.68%
2	2-Chloro-4,6-dinitro-7	60	157°	„	Benzoyl	204°	Cl : 11.27	11.04
3	4-Bromo-2,6-dinitro-4	70	160°	„	„	211°	Br : 21.08	21.85
4	3-Methyl-2, 4, 6-Trinitro-3	62	138°	„	Acetyl	249°	N : 19.91	19.73
5	2-Iodo-4-nitro-9	12	105°	Reddish yellow	„	139°	I : 41.63	41.50
6	4-Iodo-2-nitro-10	20	123°	Orange-yellow	„	123°	I : 41.66	41.50

*The number refers to those listed in Table I.

Reaction with Hydrazine Hydrate.—To a solution of substituted phenylazide in absolute ethanol was added an equivalent quantity of hydrazine hydrate solution in small amounts at a time with vigorous shaking, maintaining the temperature at about 20°; the mixture was then left overnight. The substituted hydrazine formed was separated, washed with water, and crystallised from ethanol. In case of azide 5 and 6 (Table II), the reaction mixture was refluxed for an hour to obtain the corresponding hydrazines (Table III).

TABLE III

*Azide No.	Phenylhydrazine formed.	Yield.	M.P.	Colour.
1	4-Chloro-2,6-dinitro-6	20%	138°	Reddish yellow
2	2-Chloro-4,6-dinitro-11	70	190°	Yellow
3	4-Bromo-2,6-dinitro-6	22	142°	Reddish yellow
4	2,4,6-Trinitro-3-methyl-12	65	174°	Golden yellow
5	2-Iodo-4-nitro-6	10	148°	yellow
6	4-Iodo-2-nitro-13	15	122°	Red

*The number of azides corresponds to those listed in Table I.

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